

	THE SOIL BIODIVERSITY AND FUNCTIONALITY OF MEDITERRANEAN OLIVE GROVES					
	DELIVERABLE					
	Title	Land management and soil erosion in olive cultivation				
	D.3.3		Publication date		Version	1
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The soil biodiversity and functionality of mediterranean olive groves

Deliverable 3.3

Land management and soil erosion in olive cultivation

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Executive Summary

Mediterranean olive orchards are highly vulnerable to soil erosion due to their frequent occurrence on sloping terrain, sparse ground cover, and the prevalence of intensive management practices. Addressing soil degradation in these systems requires land-use-specific, spatially explicit, and scalable assessment approaches that capture both management diversity and erosion processes across multiple scales. This deliverable responds to that need by developing and applying a multi-scale framework to assess soil erosion in olive cultivation across the EU Mediterranean.

Earth observation data from Sentinel-2 were used to derive management-relevant vegetation and surface condition indicators for olive orchards through annual temporal composites. These indicators captured spatial and seasonal variability in ground cover, bare soil exposure, and vegetation dynamics. Data-driven clustering and principal component analysis revealed distinct management regimes across Mediterranean olive-growing regions.

The WP3 group implemented a large-sample analytical strategy based on the integration of IACS olive orchard parcel data with the LUCAS survey framework, enabling pan-Mediterranean assessment at a management-relevant spatial scale. Land-use-specific refinements of a RUSLE-based erosion model were used to develop initial land-use specific erosion rates which were comparable to experimental plot values. Comparison with vegetation and surface condition indicators emphasised the consistent associations with modelled erosion rates across Mediterranean olive orchards.

To complement large-scale modelling, a semi-automatic workflow for land-use-specific, process-based modelling was developed and applied using WEPPcloud at selected sites. Target watersheds were identified from the pan-Mediterranean sample to represent contrasting erosion and management conditions and further applied at a SOIL O-LIVE pilot site. WEPP simulations provided detailed hydrological and sediment outputs, including runoff, hillslope sediment delivery, and channel sediment transport. A simple sensitivity analysis demonstrated high model sensitivity to soil erosion parameters such as rill and interrill erodibility, critical shear stress, and soil depth, necessitating refined parameterisation using field and survey data.

Overall, this deliverable provides a scalable, reproducible and transferable framework for land-use-specific, process-based assessment of soil degradation due to erosion in Mediterranean olive cultivation. The results support improved erosion risk identification, inform targeted soil conservation strategies, and contribute directly to SOIL O-LIVE objectives by linking management practices, erosion processes, and policy-relevant spatial assessment across scales.

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List of acronyms and abbreviations

CORINE	CORINE Land Cover (CLC)
EU	European Union
GIS	Geographic information system
FVC	Fractional vegetation cover
LPIS/GSAA	Land Parcel Identification System / GeoSpatial Aid Application
LUCAS	Land use and land cover survey
UNIROMA3	Università degli Studi Roma Tre
WP3	Work Package 3
EO	Earth Observation
RUSLE	Revised Universal Soil Loss Equation
WEPP	Water Erosion Prediction Project
WEPPcloud	WEPP implemented in cloud-based workflow
PCA	Principal Component Analysis
K-means	K-means clustering
t/ha/yr	Tonnes per hectare per year

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1 Introduction

Olive groves (*Olea europaea*), termed also olive orchards, are landscapes of immense cultural and economic value in the Mediterranean. Due to their frequently sparse natural vegetation, sloping terrain, and intermittent rainfall conditions, Mediterranean olive orchards have a naturally high risk of soil erosion compared to other geographic regions of Europe (Nadal-Romero and García-Ruiz, 2025). This inherent natural vulnerability to erosion is further amplified by conventional management practices such as tillage, physical and chemical vegetation removal, cultivation in large homogeneous field parcels, and the absence of terracing. In managed orchards, both vegetation removal and soil disturbance via tillage are critical factors, reducing soil's cohesion, infiltration capacity and organic matter content, leaving them exposed to potentially extreme rainfall events which occur during Mediterranean Spring and Autumn (Nadal-Romero and García-Ruiz, 2025). To ensure their long-term sustainability and economic resilience in changing climate conditions, sustainable land management is a necessary consideration to mitigate potentially extreme soil erosion rates (Borrelli et al., 2025).

Olive orchard management practices in the EU Mediterranean vary widely due to climatic, environmental, and socioeconomic gradients, making large-scale, spatially explicit analysis essential. Climate and land-use change (Tramblay & Somot, 2018), alongside policy and socioeconomic pressures, further shape management decisions and soil degradation patterns across the region (García-Ruiz et al., 2013; Nadal-Romero & García-Ruiz, 2025). This deliverable addresses the evaluation of land-use specific soil erosion by combining LUCAS survey data and IACS parcel records to develop a pan-Mediterranean overview of olive orchard management and associated soil erosion rates, enabling multi-scale analysis and policy-relevant environmental assessment.

This work by the WP3 group built on the data foundation of D3.2 (“Mapping tool box to assess land management impact”), which set out a user-friendly application for analysing the distributions and correlations of multiple environmental variables (e.g. topographic, climate and land cover) in olive orchards. This represents an application and functional extension of the toolbox, integrating land management with soil erosion modelling in olive orchards. The design follows a practical approach to first produce land-use specific ad-hoc refinements of model factors relevant to the large-scale RUSLE-based soil erosion estimations in Mediterranean Europe (Panagos et al., 2015), followed by in-depth process-based modelling at targeted sites. The present document provides a structured report of the work carried out, focusing on objectives, methodological choices, and results. Detailed technical implementation, parameter settings, and intermediate analyses are documented in an accompanying Jupyter notebook in the Python programming language for internal usage.

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2 Material and Methodology

2.1 Data Integration Framework: IACS and LUCAS

In D3.2, the WP3 group developed a hybrid data framework by integrating IACS (implemented nationally through LPIS/GSA systems) with LUCAS. By integrating both data streams and sampling designs, the hybrid sampling framework capitalises on the strengths of both systems, namely the precise, object-based geographical definition of agricultural management units from IACS and the harmonized, in-situ data and robust statistical design from LUCAS.

Table 1: An overview of the LPIS/GSAA available from D3.2 (“Mapping tool box to assess land management impact”) for download on Zenodo.

Country	Data type	No. of parcels	Area (km ²)	year	Data source
Croatia	GSA	69,471	173.6	2022	APPRRR
France	GSA	19,425	135.7	2022	IGN
Greece	GSA	1,074,512	3,531.6	2023	Opekepe
Italy	LPIS	1,073,198	8,340.3	2022	Agea
Portugal	GSA	401,561	3,088.4	2021	IFAP
Slovenia	GSA	3,287	8.5	2022	RKG
Spain	GSA	3,738,409	26,494.2	2022	FEGA
Total		6,379,863	41,772.3		

2.1.1 Rationale for an Object-Based Approach

Long standing Land Use/Land Cover (LULC) products, such as CORINE, provide standardised, medium-resolution (100 m), pixel-based classifications. While valuable for large-area assessments, their resolution is often insufficient for identifying specific agricultural management practices at the field and landscape level. Higher-resolution, pixel-based predictions (e.g., from 10-meter Sentinel data) offer the necessary granularity but lack an inherent linkage to management entities. While having numerous advantages, this spatial representation of land limits interpretability for non-specialists and hinders the integration of data on agricultural subsidies and environmental impact.

In contrast, the object-based cultivation data from IACS/GSA defines discrete management units (parcels) linked to single farming entities, allowing conceptual simplicity, spatial interpretability and modular augmentation with ancillary geospatial data. For instance, linking IACS parcels with the LUCAS modules enriches the statistical sample of parcels with in-situ measurements including soil properties (Orgiazzi et al., 2018), photo interpretations (D’Andrimont et al., 2022),

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and erosion observations (Borrelli et al., 2025). The work of the WP3 group leveraged this object-based expandability for improved soil health and environmental assessments, providing a foundation for circular feedback.

2.1.2 Statistical Sampling Design

The WP3 group embedded the sampling design for this study within the LUCAS statistical framework, which is optimised for in-situ land use monitoring across the European Union. The coupled IACS-LUCAS sampling procedure can be broadly defined as:

A Master Sample: A master sample of olive orchard parcels was first defined by spatially overlaying the IACS/GSA data with the 2-km LUCAS master grid. This initial overlay identified 10,405 unique olive orchard management units located within the grid.

Stratified Internal Sampling: Within the master sample, the LUCAS protocol selects a portion of points per stratum for each survey cycle. Over multiple triennial cycles, LUCAS iteratively populates the grid with observations at varying rates during each survey.

Coupled Data Availability: Consequently, a given IACS parcel in the master sample may currently possess zero, one, or multiple LUCAS observations, depending on its prior selection in the stratified sample. However, this structure ensures that all sites within the master sample remain candidates for future LUCAS surveys, supporting long-term monitoring.

In addition to this coupled IACS-LUCAS sample, SOIL O-LIVE pilot site geometries were added for the easy portability of methods between IACS and pilot site parcels.

Figure 1: A count of the number of olive orchard parcels analysed in this study per NUTS3 region. Parcels are sampled based on a spatial overlay between the LUCAS master grid and field parcels with registered olive cultivations through the IACS system.

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2.2 Land use and land cover analysis using Earth Observation

2.2.1 Multitemporal satellite data for management indicators

The WP3 group generated a set of targeted spectral indices composites for olive orchards. In addition to tree density, the critical management factor influencing the soil erosion risk is the inter-tree ground cover management. Practices such as tillage, herbicide application, and mowing create potentially distinct, temporally dynamic signatures of vegetation greenness and soil exposure which are visible from space. Vegetation dynamics are quantifiable from Sentinel-2 time series data due to the clear signature of vegetation in the visible red and near infrared areas of the electromagnetic spectrum (Bolton et al., 2020; Frampton et al., 2013) and the short-wave infrared (SWIR) region for non-photosynthetic vegetation cover (NPVC) dynamics (Azzari et al., 2019). In Mediterranean Europe, a generally low year-round cloud cover compared to Northern Europe is furthermore advantageous for optical remote sensing studies of vegetation dynamics which rely on an optimal number of cloud-free observations (Lewińska et al., 2024).

Figure 2: An example of a Sentinel-2 mean annual NDVI composite in Southern Spain, showing the combination of 10-meter pixel composites and the sampled field parcels which represent the olive orchard management units.

2.2.2) Sentinel-2 data processing

As outlined in D3.2, Copernicus Sentinel-2 satellite data (MultiSpectral Instrument (MSI), Level-2A surface reflectance data bottom of the atmosphere) was pre-processed and extracted using a standard Google Earth Engine (GEE) workflow (Gorelick et al., 2017). The WP3 group extracted temporal composites of all available cloud-free observations for the year 2022, by first filtering Sentinel-2 tiles at the scene level and then applying a probability-based (*s2cloudless*) pixel-wise cloud (Skakun et al., 2022).

The WP3 group simplified the processing and extraction of time series of Sentinel-2 data, using temporal compositing (i.e. time series collapsing) in GEE to describe the statistics (e.g. the

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minimum, maximum, median and standard deviation) of the time series of each pixel adapted to extract specific features of the time series. For example, if green cover is maintained during the year, NDVI is high with limited intra-annual variability. On the other hand, if bare soil is maintained via targeted vegetation removal to remove species competition, NDVI is low with limited intra-annual variability. In management situations with periodic transitions between bare and vegetated conditions, considerable variability in NDVI will be present. Combining multiple targeted spectral indices in this way was designed to give multiple interpretations of the management situation via biophysical indicators of management (e.g. green vegetation, non-photosynthetic vegetation and bare soil).

2.2.3) Management-relevant composite generation

The WP3 group generated statistical composites of Sentinel-2 covering the European Mediterranean for: (i) the Normalised Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), sensitive to chlorophyll and green vegetation, (ii) the Normalised Difference Tillage Index (NDTI), sensitive to senescent (yellow) vegetation and residues, and (iii) the Bare Soil Index (BSI), indicating exposed bare soil. These statistical composite features were chosen based on their management-relevant characterisation of the soil surface condition which offer insights into the management cycle (Table 2).

Table 2: The statistical temporal composite layers produced in the study based on the NDVI, NDTI and BSI. Temporal composites are generated pixel-wise by computing each statistical metric over the annual pixel time series.

Spectral index	Spatial aggregation	Temporal aggregation	Feature proxy
NDVI	Median	Minimum	Minimum vegetation cover in the year
NDVI	Median	Mean	Mean vegetation cover in the year
NDVI	Median	Maximum	Maximum vegetation cover in the year
NDVI	Median	Std. Deviation	Variability in vegetation cover in the year
NDTI	Median	Minimum	Minimum senescent vegetation cover in the year
BSI	Median	Max	Maximum bare soil presence in the year

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2.3 Statistical analysis of management indicators

To analyse dominant trends related to management indices in the sample of olive orchard parcels (Table 2), The WP3 group undertook several statistical analyses to identify dominant populations and trends in the data. Prior to both statistical analyses, spectral indices distributions were rescaled between 0 and 1 for algorithmic robustness. The WP3 group additionally undertook photo interpretation of the LUCAS 2022 photos repository made in olive orchards, visually identifying signs of soil tillage as a validation dataset for the management indicators.

2.3.1 K-means cluster analysis

K-means (Lloyd's) clustering is a commonly used method to group items based on similarity without prior information. Being a highly common method for unsupervised (i.e. without provided labels) classification, k-means was implemented to identify and separate management populations of olive orchards based on the statistical Sentinel-2 composites (Table 2).

2.3.2 Principal component analysis

Secondly, the WP3 group applied principal component analysis (PCA) to reduce the dimensionality of the spectral index composites (Table 2). PCA decomposes the correlated input variables into a set of orthogonal components that capture the maximum variance in the data, thereby generating metrics which capture the most valuable information in the data. The resulting components (e.g., PC1, PC2, PC3...) are ranked by the proportion of variance they explain, enabling efficient extraction of dominant temporal-spectral patterns. By further reducing the dimensionality of the data, PCA allows interpretable pattern recognition, allowing visualisations of the spatial patterns in the management-relevant indices.

2.4 Additional input variables

In addition to land use and land cover indices from Sentinel-2, the WP3 group extracted multiple variables from D.3.2 which have relevance for climatology, management conditions and erosion. Each variable was extracted based on a spatial aggregation (e.g. the mean, median, maximum and minimum) for each olive orchard parcel. To generate soil loss estimates, slope length (LS) factor, rainfall erosivity (R) factor and the soil erodibility (K) factor were combined to predict the mean annual soil loss rate according to the RUSLE model (Renard et al., 1997).

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Table 3: A full list of environmental variables pre-processed and included in the online O-live Dashboard v1.0, from D3.2.

Category	Variable
Topographic	Altitude
	Slope
	Aspect
	LS factor
	Gravelius Index
Climate	Precipitation
	Air temperature
	Soil moisture
	Soil temperature
	Surface runoff
	Snow depth
	Wind Speed
Land use/cover	Mean NDVI
	Minimum NDVI
	Maximum NDVI
	Standard Deviation NDVI
	Minimum NDTI
	Mean BSI
Soil	Soil texture
	SOC
	Bulk Density
	Nutrients (e.g. N, P, K)
	Contaminants (e.g. As, Hg, Cu, Co)
	Chemical Properties (e.g. pH, CaCO ₃ , CEC)
	Soil Depth
	K Factor
	Wind Erodible Fraction

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2.5) Soil erosion assessment

2.5.1) Estimating fractional vegetation cover from satellite data

The WP3 group implemented a Fractional Vegetation Cover (FVC) estimation method using the time series composites of Sentinel-2 imagery and the Relative Abundance (RA) algorithm (Gao et al., 2020). In olive orchards, the inter-row FVC is the primary factor influenced by management practices (e.g., mowing, tillage, herbicide application) relevant to erosion control.

The RA algorithm calculates FVC based on a linear scaling between the NDVI values of bare soil ($NDVI_S$) and full vegetation cover ($NDVI_\infty$):

$$FVC = \left(\frac{NDVI - NDVI_\infty}{NDVI_S - NDVI_\infty} \right)^{Kp/Kvi}, \quad (1)$$

The scaling coefficient Kp/Kvi was set to the standard 0.6175 for NDVI, as established by Baret et al. (1995). The NDVI value used in Equation (1) was the mean annual value derived from all available Sentinel-2 observations for the year (see Table 2).

A primary challenge in applying this model to olive orchards is the prevalence of mixed pixels, which contain mixed spectral signals from both tree canopies and inter-row areas. To address this, the WP3 group implemented a parcel-level strategy to define NDVI endmember values, combining fixed thresholds with data-driven extraction from Sentinel-2 time series.

2.5.2 Parcel scale erosion metrics

2.5.2.1 Model fitting and parameter refinement

The WP3 group first predicted soil erosion rates using the common Revised Universal Soil Loss Equation (RUSLE) model (Renard et al., 1997), which is applied in the current generation of EU soil erosion estimates (Panagos et al., 2015). All parameters except the land use parameter (C-factor) were implemented with the current generation of pan-European input datasets (Panagos et al., 2015), which facilitates standardised and comparable erosion risk assessments across the European Union.

In short, the RUSLE is a multiplicative model that estimates average annual soil loss as a function of climate, soil, topography, and land cover:

$$A = R K L S C P, \quad (2)$$

where A is the average annual soil loss ($t \text{ ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$), R is the rainfall-runoff erosivity factor ($MJ \text{ mm ha}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$), K is the soil erodibility factor ($t \text{ ha h ha}^{-1} \text{ MJ}^{-1} \text{ mm}^{-1}$), L and S are the unitless slope length and steepness factors, respectively, C is the cover-management factor (unitless), and P is the support practice factor (unitless). For this study, the P -factor was set to 1, indicating no support practices (e.g. terracing and stone walls) were modelled.

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For the olive orchard parcels, object-based erosion rates were generated by calculating the mean annual FVC composite for each parcel (Section 2.5.1) and using it to derive a parcel-specific C-factor. For this work, the β parameter was calibrated to a local land-use specific optimum using the strategy outlined in Matthews et al., (2023). Within this deliverable, these concepts were extended and implemented. Specifically, the WP3 group adapted this calibration strategy by using experimental plot soil erosion rate data to obtain a land-use specific optimum based on the input FVC predictions (Section 2.5.1).

The C-factor (i.e. the annually aggregated vegetation parameter representing management) was calculated from the mean annual FVC (converted to percentage vegetation cover, PVC) using a reverse exponential function (Matthews et al., 2023). This well-established relationship, represented in empirical to process-based models (Gyssels et al., 2005) and with high sensitivity in olive orchards (Peñuela et al., 2025 – in review), describes the non-linear decrease in soil loss with increasing vegetation cover. It captures the disproportionately high erosion risk associated with low cover conditions (e.g., < 30% PVC):

$$C = e^{(-\beta \times PVC)}, \quad (3)$$

The scaling parameter β controls the sensitivity of the predicted soil loss to changes in vegetation cover to increase the sensitivity of soil erosion to vegetation cover.

2.5.2.2 Calibration of the C-factor large scale assessments in olive orchards

The sensitivity of the RUSLE cover-management factor to vegetation cover varies with vegetation type and stratification, management practices, and the characteristics of the FVC determined by the remote sensing (Matthews et al., 2023). To determine a representative value for Mediterranean olive orchards at a large scale, the WP3 group carried out a calibration exercise using a random subsample of field parcels (section 2.1).

The calibration was informed by experimentally derived relationships between vegetation cover and soil erosion rates reported in the literature, which are compiled in recently publicly available preprint studies synthesising runoff plot measurements from Mediterranean olive orchards (e.g. Peñuela et al., 2025, EGU sphere preprint). Rather than using experimental models as direct validation targets, their reported erosion rate–vegetation cover behaviour was used as a reference framework to guide the adjustment of the vegetation sensitivity in the RUSLE C-factor. The objective was to ensure that parcel-scale soil erosion estimates produced by the RUSLE model exhibit vegetation responses consistent with compiled experimental soil erosion rate observations, while retaining the multivariate structure of the RUSLE formulation.

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2.5.3 Large-scale model assessment and site-specific process-based modelling

The WP3 group undertook an independent comparison of the soil erosion rates using the withheld parcels. In addition, a comparison of soil loss rates was made compared to with a standard (Matthews et al., 2023), uncalibrated C-factor (i.e. -0.04), allowing an assessment of the improvement in the soil erosion rates achieved by the C-factor calibration routine. Thereafter, the WP3 group estimated soil erosion rates for all sampled olive orchard parcels. In all cases, the median spatially aggregated value of each factor was applied to obtain parcel estimates of soil erosion rates.

Figure 3: The model application strategy for pan-Mediterranean, land-use specific modelling using RUSLE, followed by site-specific WEPPcloud application.

Following the first estimation of soil loss rates using the RUSLE, a process-based assessment of soil erosion was carried out at selected locations using the WEPP model (version wepp_31131a7). The WEPP model (Flanagan & Nearing 1995), implemented within WEPPcloud (Lew et al., 2022), is a tool that predicts soil erosion and sediment yield due to rainfall-runoff generation, interrill and rill erosion, and sediment transport and deposition. The model parameterisation scheme combined with the parcel-based sampling scheme allows land-use specific parameterisation, allowing the selection or automatic parameterisation of land use type using the WEPPcloud workflow (running the wepppy software). The spatial structure divides micro-catchments into hillslope and channel units, allowing users to access both hillslope and channel level simulations.

Implementation was undertaken in the multi-year mode over the default 100-years using the WEPPcloud eu-disturbed workflow (Lew et al., 2022), which performs automatic watershed delineation based on a digital elevation model. Climate was parameterised in the workflow from publicly available datasets for Europe. Within WEPPcloud, key sources of uncertainty include the generalisation of management scenarios and spatial heterogeneity of the land surface. To mitigate this, the model was parameterised using land use information informed by Sentinel-2

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imagery to distinguish perennially covered from tilled surface conditions, illustrating how satellite data can inform the assignment of land management characteristics for process-based modelling in olive orchards.

The WP3 group applied a tiered modelling workflow in which calibrated, computationally efficient RUSLE estimates of long-term average soil loss (Section 3.3), together with land management indicators relevant to olive cultivation (Section 3.2), were first used to identify different risk levels of soil erosion. These locations were subsequently analysed using the more computationally intensive, process-based WEPP model to provide detailed insights into erosion processes under Mediterranean olive-growing conditions.

3. Results

Using the multiscale methodology adapted for land-use specific soil erosion assessment in olive orchards, the WP3 group generated multiple interim results relating to land management and soil erosion. The work done on land management and soil erosion is evidenced firstly for the entire coupled IACS-LUCAS sample for olive orchards, and secondly at selected sites using process-based modelling.

3.1) Indicative spatial trends in erosion rates

3.1.1) Evaluation of olive orchard erosion rates

Via the land-use specific calibration routine, the WP3 group estimated erosion rates across the sample (Figure 4). The tested calibration scheme better reflected experimental studies (46 % increase in the R^2 value) by improving the vegetation cover component which dominates the soil erosion response in olive orchards. For erosion risk identification across the EU-Mediterranean, the land-use specific refinement can better inform large-scale, simplistic assessments.

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Figure 4: Changes in the distribution of soil erosion rates in olive orchards due to soil loss rate calibrations using an experimental model.

While differences remain between large-scale model estimates and relationships derived from plot-scale experiments, these results illustrate the potential of land-use-specific parameterisation to improve the interpretability and process-representation of regional soil erosion patterns in olive orchards compared to the use of unadjusted, generic parameters. The analysis is intended to provide a comparative assessment of model behaviour rather than a formal validation of erosion rates.

3.2) Vegetation and management trends across the European olive orchards

3.2.1) Patterns in management-relevant vegetation dynamics

The WP3 group undertook an analysis of land management proxies in olive orchards across the EU Mediterranean. Figure (5) presents spatial aggregations of the management-relevant spectral indices from Sentinel-2 (Table 2), aggregated at the NUTS3 level to show the broad spatial patterns across olive producing regions. The analysed variables correspond to annual statistical composites of Normalised Difference Vegetation Index (minimum, maximum, standard deviation and mean), Normalised Difference Tillage Index (minimum) and Bare Soil Index (maximum), which quantify the dynamics of green vegetation cover, the minimum residual non photosynthetic vegetation cover in the year, and the maximum bare soil exposure. These indices provide complimentary information on seasonal vegetation dynamics and surface conditions, serving as proxies for management conditions.

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The WP3 group found substantial areas of Spain to have low vegetation cover with low interannual dynamics, suggesting little ground cover development through the year. Similarly, high values of the bare soil index (BSI; maximum) and low values of the Normalised Difference Tillage Index (NDTI; minimum) suggesting high bare soil presence with little non photosynthetic vegetation cover (NPVC), which would otherwise follow green up during growth-permitting seasons. These multiple factors point to the unique, intensively managed conditions of olive orchards in much of the Spanish territory, which have relatively low biomass dynamics through the year.

In contrast to the Spanish territory, France, Italy, Portugal and Greece show contrasting biomass dynamics with (i) higher intra-annual variability of NDVI, and (ii) higher values of minimum NDTI. The maximum BSI in the year is a proxy for the spatial patterns of more probable bare soil occurrence in the year, reflecting regions with more likely bare soil occurrence. The spatial patterns show high maximum BSI values in Portugal, Spain, regions of Southern Italy, and some regions of Greece. Outside of Spain, characterised by typically mostly low ground cover and intra-annual variability, this analysis shows the potential to identify olive cultivating regions typified by relatively higher intra-annual variability in ground cover conditions, including the occurrence of tillage which contributes to high intra-annual variability in the green vegetation cover.

Figure 5: Mean values of the management relevant spectral index statistical composites per NUTS3 region compiled in D3.2. Regional values are given based on the combined sample of olive orchard parcels per NUTS3 region.

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3.2.2) Data-driven characterisation of land management relevant variables

3.2.2.1) K-means cluster analysis

The WP3 group applied k-means data-driven clustering to characterise the dominant populations and investigate the controls on the variability within the spatiotemporal composite layers. Plotting of a data subsample of the spectral indices data showed differences between clusters (Figure 6), showing visual separability between clusters.

Figure 6: Illustrative boxplots of the management relevant spectral index composites from a random 5 % of parcels. Names are formatted according to the variable name, temporal aggregation range and spatial aggregation method (e.g. NDVI min 1y median p is the minimum NDVI in a year for the median value per parcel).

At the regional scale, the clusters illustrate the aggregated spatial patterns of clusters per NUTS3 region to describe regions dominated by one cluster or showing a mixture. In Figure (7; upper) darker colours represent more consistent cluster assignments for all olive parcels in each NUTS3 region, while values intermediate colours represent a degree of heterogeneity within the sample.

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Figure 7: Illustrative geographical distributions per NUTS3 region of the; i) mean K-means cluster value of the olive orchard parcel population (upper), ii) mean value for PCA component 1 (middle), and iii) mean value for PCA 2 (lower).

3.2.2.2) PCA dimensionality reduction

The WP3 group applied principal component analysis (PCA) to analyse the main patterns of variability within the set of management-relevant ground cover indicators. A benefit of PCA applied to interpretable, management related variables, is its ability to extract associations between variables and identify the principal drivers of variability.

Interpreting the PCA loadings, Figure (8) shows PCA1 to be primarily influenced by indicators of the absolute vegetation cover, such as NDVI and NDTI. In contrast, PCA2 is influenced primarily by the intra-annual variability of vegetation cover dynamic and the maximum bare soil

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presence within the year. These components were mapped at the regional (NUTS3) level to illustrate broad spatial trends in the parcel-level values (Figure 7).

Exploratory, qualitative comparisons of the principal components with a random subsample of interpreted tillage observations (presence or absence) at 618 LUCAS 2022 usable site photos by the WP3 group shows that the PCA components show qualitative consistency with tillage occurrences at LUCAS sites (Figure 8). This illustrative comparison highlights the potential of PCA-based indicators of simplistic Sentinel-2 composites to support the interpretation of ground cover management in olive orchards.

Figure 8: Illustrative examples. Upper: biplots of the 2 dominant principal components with a random selected of 5% of olive orchards. Lower: boxplots of Principal Components 1 and 2 compared to a random subsample of photo interpretations of soil tillage made by UNIROMA3 at LUCAS 2022 survey sites in the olive orchard survey sample.

3.3) Erosion rates in relation to land use and vegetation management

3.3.1) Statistical properties of soil loss in olive orchards

The work undertaken by the WP3 group builds on the establishment of vegetation cover as an important factor affecting soil erosion rates in experimental settings (Peñuela et al., 2025, EGU sphere preprint). Using the adapted RUSLE model, the WP3 group analysed the regional

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patterns of soil erosion rates in relation to ground cover. To give an illustrative example, a random sample of parcel sites were evaluated in Spain, showing the interlinkages between vegetation management and soil erosion rates.

Figure 9: Illustrative statistical plots of the modelled soil erosion rates (left) in relation to management populations identified using k-means cluster analysis (right) for a random subsample of olive orchard field parcels in Spain.

The WP3 group analysed the distribution of predicted erosion rates for the olive orchard parcel sample for the whole population and grouped by vegetation management cluster (Figure 9). To illustrate the modelled erosion behaviour, the random subsample of parcels from Spain is plotted, showing the general erosion response as well as the importance of vegetation management. These patterns highlight the sensitivity of the land-use specific RUSLE modelling approach to vegetation-related inputs, where lower indicator values are typically associated with higher erosion rates. These results exemplify the potential of Earth observation data to support the consistent characterisation of spatial patterns in vegetation-related erosion behaviour across Mediterranean olive cultivation systems.

3.3.2) Associations between management and gully erosion in olive orchards

For the year 2022, LUCAS contains a gully observations module which observes incisional erosion features at LUCAS sites (Borrelli et al., 2025). Their occurrence is shown to strongly link to vegetation cover across all land uses (Borrelli et al., 2025). At the NUTS3 level, the WP3 group explored the broad spatial patterns of the occurrence of gullies in olive orchards to provide contextual insight between large-scale vegetation, RUSLE estimations and gully observations (Figure 10). The WP3 group undertook an exploratory analysis, identifying co-occurrence with the management-based indices in this work at LUCAS survey sites (section 3.2.2). The WP3 group further compared the predicted soil erosion rates in all LUCAS 2022 olive orchard parcels with gully occurrence, finding it to be a useful contextual indicator for gully susceptible olive orchard parcels (Figure 10; lower).

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Figure 10: An illustrative geographic overview of gully erosion occurrence in olive orchards. Upper: A relative NUTS3 level count of gully erosion features (“SURVEY_GULLY_SIGNS”) in the LUCAS 2022 survey. Lower: Illustrative boxplots of i) the distribution gullies observed in olive orchard parcels per NUTS3 region per cluster group (1 and 2), and ii) the predicted RUSLE erosion rate in sites with (1) and without (0) observed gullies.

3.3.3) Process-based modelling at selected sites

This section addresses the land-use specific, process-based modelling framework to quantify soil erosion processes in olive orchard conditions. The WP3 group applied a multi-scale workflow with a set of conditional filters to select land-use specific target sites for semi-automatic process-based modelling in multiple targeted watersheds using WEPP. The approach consists of site scoping and selection from the pan-Mediterranean sample of olive orchards, followed by watershed delineation, WEPP parameterisation and model running. The workflow was initially applied across six sites in the EU Mediterranean region based on the coupled IACS-LUCAS

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sample, representing a range of relative erosion risk and land management conditions (section 3.4). For demonstration purposes, two sites were selected using the workflow for evaluation, representing relatively higher and lower modelled erosion conditions using the RUSLE (Figure 11).

Figure 11: Illustrative examples of process-based modelling using WEPPcloud in two selected sites to model soil erosion. WEPPcloud generates numerous outputs including runoff, interrill and rill soil loss, hillslope sediment delivery, channel sediment transport, and total sediment yield.

Figure (11) demonstrates example outputs from WEPPcloud for the example sites over a 100-year period, highlighting the contrasting hillslope sediment delivery simulated. WEPP discretises the micro watershed into individual hillslopes, allowing olive orchard specific analysis in mixed land use situations. Examples of the analysed outputs are recurrence intervals for precipitation (millimetres) and the total sediment delivered from hillslopes (hill sed del; tonnes), which represent the important driving and response factors for soil erosion.

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Figure 12: Examples of output from WEPPcloud for a selected Spanish pilot site, giving multiple simulations for the hillslopes (upper), stream channel (middle) over the time period of simulation (lower).

The WP3 group further applied the workflow at a Spanish Soil-Olive pilot site, obtaining multiple hydrological and soil erosion outputs (Figure 12). As a process-based model, WEPP explicitly simulates hydrological and soil detachment processes, enabling detailed analysis of runoff generation and sediment transport mechanisms. Using WEPPcloud, a simple 10-scenario sensitivity analysis was undertaken, varying the interrill erodibility, rill erodibility and critical shear stress parameters (Basso et al., 2025). Simplistic sensitivity analysis acted as a starting point for future work on the identification of important model parameters, which can be used to prioritise data collection within the project.

The undertaken analysis in WEPP by the WP3 group gave insights into the high model sensitivity (i.e. inducing over an order of magnitude change in the soil erosion rate) of the simulated hillslope soil erosion rates to variations in sensitive parameters (e.g. rill erodibility, interrill erodibility, and critical shear stress). These parameters are recognised in other studies to strongly influence the water runoff and soil erosion response (Basso et al., 2025). Additional testing showed parameters such as soil depth to be important for the simulated runoff and soil erosion, particularly given that olive trees can grow in varying soil depths. The sensitivity analysis sheds light on the parameters relevant for simulating soil erosion in olive orchards, where managed soil surface conditions and shallow soils strongly influence interrill and rill processes. Within this context, the developed spatial approach demonstrates the utility of refined parameterisation using measured data from Soil O-olive pilot sites and harmonised LUCAS soil measurements. The developed, multi-scale modelling strategy for process-based modelling, provides a transferable methodology for

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upscaling, allowing refined parameterisation of WEPP for assessing soil degradation in Mediterranean olive systems beyond the analysed watersheds.

3.4) Implications and deliverable interlinkages

3.4.1) Implications

The WP3 group applied a multi-scale methodology to analyse ground cover management dynamics and quantify soil erosion in olive orchard field parcels. These outputs directly support downstream SOIL O-LIVE activities, including pilot site assessments, indicator development, and scenario analysis. By building a parcel sampling structure based on both IACS field registrations of olive orchards combined with the LUCAS sampling structure, the analysis strategy optimises the available ground-truth data for pan-EU Mediterranean studies while generating predictions at a management-relevant spatial scale (i.e. the field parcel unit) and using the IACS data stream which distinguishes actively farmed land from abandoned, undeclared land units.

The parcel-scale RUSLE predictions offer insights for assessing potentially unsustainable soil degradation rates due to soil erosion in different Mediterranean regions (Table 4). For example, filtering the parcel sample to identify areas with relatively high predicted erosion rates (Figure 13) can be used to highlight potential areas for downstream research purposes. The examples further illustrate how areas with higher sheet and rill erosion using the RUSLE model may contextually coincide with gully-like features.

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Figure 13: Illustrative examples of olive orchard parcels with high relatively higher predicted soil erosion rates at the field parcel scale. High resolution imagery from Google Earth™ is used to demonstrate generic planar and incisional erosion patterns.

The hierarchical data framework applied builds data-driven characterisations of management practices in olive orchards which are highly scalable due to their use of Sentinel-2 data. As illustrated in Figure (13), the dimensionality reduction and classifier algorithms trained on the pan-EU Mediterranean sample of olive orchards can be consistently transferred to the pilot sites in the SOIL O-LIVE, allowing potential use as simplified environmental features for other activities within the project.

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Figure 14: Principal Component Analysis (PCA) extended to the Soil O-LIVE pilot sites using the developed algorithm from the LUCAS-IACS data sample.

3.4.2) Limitations and future improvements

The WP3 group identified several limitations in the work which represent scope for further refinements in large-scale assessment. Firstly, a limitation of the model-intercomparison based calibration approach of RUSLE is that the model of Peñuela et al., (2025 – in review) represents the soil loss response to vegetation cover. This simplification, which doesn't explicitly account for other variables such as slope, climate and soil type, means that additional variability is not accounted for. Secondly, a widely acknowledged limitation of the RUSLE for large scale modelling is its plot based experimental design, which limits its applicability in conditions where interrill and rill erosion are not the only active soil erosion processes (e.g. in gully dominated areas). Lastly, the LUCAS-based sampling scheme allows a statistically robust quantification of the diversity in management conditions across olive cultivating areas in the EU Mediterranean.

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While extending this analysis to soil erosion rates gives valuable insights into the statistical properties and drivers of soil loss, an extension to the full extent of olive cultivating land would give a more robust evaluation of the soil loss rates.

Despite the current limitations of large-scale erosion rate estimations in olive orchards, the semi-automatic, multi-scale modelling approach developed by the WP3 group facilitated more detailed, process-based modelling at olive orchard sites of interest. The interlinkage between satellite data and land-use-specific parameterisation in the multi-scale workflow facilitated the exploration of management conditions in olive orchards based on their impact on soil erosion. Future improvements include refined soil parameterisation using field-specific measurements, as well as the inclusion of increased information on management practices within the land-use specific context. Together, this process-based modelling provides actionable insights for planning targeted soil conservation measures, optimising orchard management, and supporting the long-term sustainability of olive orchards.

4) Conclusion

The WP3 group developed a large sample-based approach to quantify the management diversity and erosion rates in olive orchards in the EU Mediterranean, complemented by site-specific process-based modelling at target sites. In doing so, this deliverable fulfils its objective of providing a land-use specific, process-based assessment framework for soil degradation due to erosion in olive orchards. Management indicators derived from temporal composites of Sentinel-2, targeted towards management features, demonstrated consistent relationships between vegetation dynamics and management in olive orchards. Furthermore, linking management indicators with erosion rates across the EU-Mediterranean demonstrated the connection between intensively tilled management systems and high soil erosion rates, which have geographical variability across the Mediterranean.

The combined sampling approach applied, based on olive cultivating IACS parcels coinciding with the LUCAS sampling grid, considerably augments the information content at the pan-EU Mediterranean scale and allows intercomparisons between erosion rate predictions and gully erosion occurrence from harmonised survey data. Overall, the generated workflow provides a fully reproducible and expandable framework for land-use-specific, process-based evaluation of soil degradation due to erosion in Mediterranean olive cultivation.

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